

IODINATION. PART V. STUDIES ON THE PHOTOIODINATION OF PHENYLACETYLENE IN LIGHT OF DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES IN POLAR SOLVENT.

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The kinetics and mechanism of the iodination of phenylacetylene in alcoholic solution in radiations of frequencies 366, 436 and 546 $\mu\mu$ have been studied. Results indicate that the reaction, which is unimolecular in nature, is reversible and does not proceed to completion. The temperature coefficient of the reaction is small as also the quantum efficiency.

Instances of photochemical iodination of unsaturated organic compounds in polar solvents, like alcohol, etc., are not at all found in the literature. The object of the present investigation is to study in detail the kinetics and mechanism of the iodination of phenylacetylene in alcoholic solution in light of frequencies 366, 436 and 546 $\mu\mu$. The reaction is a reversible one and does not go to completion.

The experimental procedure and arrangement have been described in the previous parts.

Merck's purest absolute alcohol was further purified by distillation over metallic calcium before use. The reaction between iodine and phenylacetylene in solution of CCl_4 does not proceed in the dark even with high initial concentrations of iodine but in alcoholic solution there is an appreciable dark reaction with high initial concentrations of iodine which has been studied in Part III of the series (*vide* p. 253). In this investigation the composition of the reaction mixtures were so chosen that there was no dark reaction during the period of investigation.

Measurement of Intensity and Extinction Coefficient of Iodine in Alcoholic Solution.

The intensity of incident radiation was measured by means of a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer as described in Part IV of the series (*vide* p. 257).

The energy of absorbed radiation was calculated according to the equation

$$I_{\text{abs.}} = I_0 (1 - 10^{-\epsilon.c.d}).$$

where $I_{\text{abs.}}$, I_0 , ϵ , c and d have their usual significance as described in Part IV. The extinction coefficient (ϵ) of iodine in alcoholic solution was determined in different wave-lengths (λ) in exactly the same way as has been described in Part IV. The values of ϵ of iodine in alcoholic solution are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I.

λ ($\mu\mu$)	...	546	436	366
	..	106.2	3742.0	5322.5

The experimental data are recorded in Tables II to V. The values of k_a have been derived from the simple monomolecular equation,

$$k_a = \frac{2.3}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where a is the initial concentration of iodine and x , the concentration of the iodo-product in gram mols per litre formed in time t seconds.

The values of k_a were found to diminish slightly with time. The absorbed energy may be considered to be practically constant and the iodo product formed may be regarded as negligible when the concentrations of iodine do not change by more than 10%. Hence values of k_a , as measured above, may be regarded as derived under conditions of constant light absorption and negligible concentration of the iodo product formed.

In the sixth vertical column of Tables II and IV are given the values of k_a and in the 7th vertical column are given the values of $k_a/I_{abs}^{1/2}$. It will be seen that $k_a/I_{abs}^{1/2}$ have always got the same value for the same monochromatic radiation.

R E S U L T S.

The effect of varying the concentrations of iodine on the velocity of reaction is shown in Table II.

λ = wave-length; a , b = initial concentrations of iodine and phenyl acetylene in gram mols per litre.

I_0 = intensity of incident radiation in ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

$I_{abs.}$ = number of quanta absorbed per c.c. per sec.

γ = quantum efficiency.

θ = temperature.

d = thickness of the cell.

TABLE II.

$\theta = 25^\circ$. $d = 0.5$ cm.

λ .	a .	b .	I_0 .	$I_{abs.}$	k_a .	$k_a/I_{abs}^{1/2}$.	γ .
366 μ	0.0077M	0.111M	182.5	68.1 $\times 10^{10}$	7.43 $\times 10^{-6}$	0.90 $\times 10^{-12}$	0.51
"	0.0157	"	"	"	7.43	0.90	1.04
"	0.0248	"	"	"	7.43	0.90	1.64
436	0.00765	0.055	628.3	279.2	7.31	0.44	0.12
"	0.0155	"	"	"	7.33	0.44	0.25
"	0.0232	"	"	"	7.30	0.44	0.37
"	0.00765	0.111	"	"	14.07	0.90	0.25
"	0.0153	"	"	"	14.67	0.88	0.49
"	0.0195	"	"	"	14.71	0.88	0.62
546	0.0078	0.111	144.3	49.2	7.00	1.00	0.62
"	0.0159	"	"	69.8	8.11	0.97	1.18
"	0.0252	"	"	76.5	8.50	0.97	1.69

From this table we see that $k_a \times 10^{12}/I_{abs}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is nearly independent of the initial concentration of iodine as well as of the wave-lengths used.

The effect of varying the concentration of the acceptor on the velocity of reaction is shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

$\theta = 25^\circ$. $d = 0.5$ cm.

λ .	a .	b .	I_0 .	I_{abs} .	k_a .	γ .
366 $\mu\mu$	0.0077M	0.055M	182.5	68.1 $\times 10^{12}$	3.75 $\times 10^{-8}$	0.26
"	"	0.111	"	"	7.43	0.51
"	"	0.167	"	"	11.28	0.77
436	0.00765	0.055	628.3	279.2	7.31	0.12
"	"	0.111	"	"	14.07	0.25
"	"	0.167	"	"	24.83	0.41
546	0.0078	0.055	144.3	49.2	4.27	0.41
"	"	0.111	"	"	7.0	0.67
"	"	0.167	"	"	12.1	1.15

From this table we see that the velocity constant is directly proportional to the concentration of the acceptor.

The effect of varying the intensity on the velocity of reaction is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

$\theta = 25^\circ$. $d = 0.5$ cm.

λ .	a .	b .	I_0 .	I_{abs} .	k_a .	$k_a/I_{abs}^{\frac{1}{2}}$	γ .
366 $\mu\mu$	0.0157M	0.111M	182.5	68.1 $\times 10^{12}$	7.43 $\times 10^{-8}$	0.90 $\times 10^{-12}$	1.04
"	"	"	91.3	34.1	5.03	0.86	1.41
436	0.0153	0.111	628.3	279.2	14.67	0.88	0.49
"	"	"	169.8	75.5	7.91	0.91	0.57
546	0.0159	0.111	144.3	69.8	8.11	0.97	1.11
"	"	"	72.2	34.1	5.74	0.98	1.62

From this table we see that the velocity constant is directly proportional to the square root of absorbed radiation.

The effect of varying the temperature on the velocity of reaction is shown in Table V.

TABLE V

 $d = 0.5 \text{ cm.}$

λ .	a .	b .	I_a .	I_{obs} .	$k_8 \times 10^8$.		v .
					$\theta = 25^\circ$	$\theta = 35^\circ$	
366 $\mu\mu$	0.0077M	0.111M	182.5	68.1 $\times 10^{12}$	7.43	7.5	1.01
436	0.00765	..	628.3	279.2	14.97	16.8	1.12
546	0.0073	..	70.0	33.0	5.45	6.21	1.14

 v = the temperature coefficient for 10° rise.

From this table we see that the temperature coefficient is nearly unity.

DISCUSSION.

The reaction has the following characteristics :—

The reaction is unimolecular with respect to iodine. The quantity k_8 which diminishes slightly with the progress of the reaction, is directly proportional to the square root of the intensity of the absorbed radiation, and increases proportionally with the increase in the concentration of the acceptor in all the three wave-lengths used. It also increases with increasing concentration of iodine at 546 $\mu\mu$ where the absorption is weak but remains constant at 436 and 366 $\mu\mu$ where the absorption is very strong. In fact $k_8 \cdot 10^{12} / I_{\text{abs}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is independent of the initial concentration of iodine and also of the three wave-lengths used in this investigation. The temperature coefficient is small, nearly unity, and the quantum efficiency is also small.

The mechanism of the reaction is the same as has been proposed in Part IV.

It has been shown in Part IV that the quantum efficiency of the photoiodination of phenylacetylene in solution of CCl_4 is very high, whereas in the present investigation it is very low. This difference in the values of the quantum efficiency indicates that the reaction has got a long chain in non-polar solvent but in polar solvent the chain length is greatly diminished.

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